

STRESS CONTOUR UTILIZATION FOR ESTIMATING INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF FIBER/MATRIX COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

The performance of fiber/matrix composite as load bearing structure does not only depend on mechanical properties of its compilers but also interfacial properties of fiber/matrix interface [1]. The failure of fiber/matrix composite frequently occurs due to the weakness of interfacial properties. Fiber/matrix interface can be divided into three conditions based on its separation which are full bonding condition, partial bonding condition, and full debonding condition. These conditions are stated on traction (t) - separation (δ) curve as shown in Fig. 1 [2]. Four parameters of interfacial properties i.e. interfacial stiffness (K_i), interfacial strength (t_i), interfacial fracture toughness (G_i), and interfacial friction coefficient (μ_i) are defined. The weakness of each parameter gives different effect to composite performance. Low K_i causes a crack in matrix propagate closer to fiber/matrix interface. Low t_i causes initial degradation of K_i due to low traction. Low G_i causes catastrophic crack failure along fiber/matrix interface. The magnitude of μ_i affects the balance of energy release rate in fiber/matrix interface. Low μ_i causes inability to prevent crack propagation. These parameters of interfacial properties have to be evaluated properly.

Many efforts have been conducted to evaluate interfacial properties [3, 4]. However, it still has problem especially inability to estimate K_i and μ_i . The existing methods in evaluating interfacial properties usually neglect K_i and μ_i which cause overestimate results of t_i and G_i . Estimating K_i and μ_i are generally difficult because it needs traction curve along fiber/matrix interface which cannot be observed experimentally. In fact, traction curve along interface can be determined by observing stress contour in matrix using photo-elasticity technique. Stress contour in matrix is theoretically built from its boundary condition which is traction

curve. By comparing stress contour obtained from experiment and simulation, overall interfacial properties can be estimated properly.

Single fiber fragmentation test (SFFT) was selected to observe stress contour due to its easiness in creating specimen. SFFT also replicates the stress transfer characteristics in real composite. When one fiber crack on SFFT appeared due to applied strain (ϵ_a) as shown in Fig. 2.a, axis symmetric model of single fiber surrounded by matrix was built using finite element method software as shown at Fig. 2.b. Several model parameters were examined previously in order to obtain appropriate model which represent condition of SFFT experiment. Inverse analysis algorithm was developed to estimate the four parameters of interfacial properties. Characteristic lengths in stress contour were found to assist in estimating interfacial properties.

Fig.1. Traction-separation curve (left) and friction coefficient curve after full debonding (right)

Fig.2. One fiber crack on SFFT (a) and axis-symmetric model (b).

2 Single Fiber Fragmentation Model

2.1 Traction at Interface

In SFFT experiment, the magnitude of matrix length (a) and matrix radius (R) at Fig. 2b are very high compared with fiber radius (r). However, large a and R in simulation increases the number of finite elements and consumes much simulation time. In order hand, small a and R causes the simulation result produce different stress contour in matrix of SFFT due to the effect of matrix edges. The optimum value which compromises those conditions should be found.

The presence of stress contour in matrix is caused by traction at interface which appeared short after fiber crack occur due to stress transfer from matrix to fiber. Free body diagram of matrix model after fiber crack occurs is shown at Fig. 3. Highest traction occurs near fiber crack and gradually decreases until no traction remain at the opposite side. This degradation forms traction curve which can be divided into two zones i.e. ineffective zone where the traction appears on interface and effective zone where no traction remains.

The length of ineffective zone which is called ineffective length (L_i) should be fully covered in SFFT model in order to obtain same stress contour between SFFT and its model. This requirement implies that a should be longer than L_i . However, determining a is not simple because L_i is influenced by geometrical parameters and mechanical properties of fiber and matrix. All influenced parameters were examined on simulations in order to investigate proper value of a .

Fig. 3 Free body diagram of matrix model and traction curve in interface

2.2 Parameters Consideration

Many parameters affecting L_i were introduced by Cox [5]. The parameters can be divided into two types i.e. geometrical parameters and mechanical properties. Each parameter was simulated to find its influence to L_i .

2.2.1 Geometrical parameters

Two geometrical parameters affecting L_i are applied strain (ϵ_a) and radius ratio (R/r). Several simulations were conducted to obtain the tendency of L_i alteration. On these simulations, mechanical properties were kept constant which are elastic modulus ratio (E_f/E_m) of 10 and Poisson's ratio (ν_m) of 0.3. The curve of L_i divided by fiber radius which is called normalized L_i was plotted in the Fig 4. These curves show that L_i alteration is not significant on the R/r more than 20. Therefore, the R/r should be higher than 20 when single fiber fragmentation model was created in order to avoid radius ratio effect. The magnitude of ϵ_a also gives significant effect to L_i which mean selected length of model should also consider ϵ_a recorded on experiment.

Fig. 4 Normalized ineffective length alteration due to geometrical parameters alteration

2.2.2 Mechanical properties

The influence of mechanical properties i.e. elastic modulus ratio (E_f/E_m) and Poisson's ratio of matrix (v_m) to L_i were also investigated. The simulations were conducted by keeping geometrical parameter as constant values i.e R/r of 20 and ε_a of 0.5%. The result of simulations is shown at Fig. 5. The curves of normalized L_i at Fig. 5 conclude that v_m give small influence compared with E_f/E_m . Therefore, the influence of v_m can be neglected. In other hand, E_f/E_m should be considered properly when single fiber fragmentation model was created.

Fig. 5 Normalized ineffective length alteration due to mechanical properties alteration

2.3 The presence of interfacial debonding

Beside geometrical parameters and mechanical properties, interfacial debonding also causes high L_i . Simulations were also conducted by adding interfacial debonding in the single fiber fragmentation model. The model parameters and simulation result are shown at Table 1 and Fig. 6. It concludes that increasing L_i is proportional to length of interfacial debonding. The simulation result indicated that length of interfacial debonding should be also considered properly.

Table 1. Geometrical parameter

Elastic modulus ratio (E_f/E_m)	10
Poisson ratio of matrix (v_m)	0.3
Radius ratio (R/r)	20
Applied strain (ε_a)	0.5%

Fig. 6 Normalized ineffective length alteration due to normalized interfacial debonding (nor.in.deb.) alteration

3 Evaluation of Interfacial Properties

3.1 Response of Stress Contour to Interfacial Properties

Tresca stress contour in matrix has relation with interfacial properties. The further problem is how to connect them properly. Theoretically, traction curve at interface responses the magnitude of interfacial properties and it also transforms Tresca stress contour in matrix. Inverse analysis can be conducted by comparing Tresca stress contour obtained from experiment and simulation. Interfacial properties are evaluated when similar contour were obtained.

Tresca stress contour is formed by four interfacial properties. However, it is not easy to estimate four interfacial properties which response similar Tresca stress contour. The inverse analysis will be less complicated if the tendency of Tresca stress contour alteration was known by changing interfacial properties. Three characteristic lengths were found by changing interfacial properties to assist inverse analysis. Several simulations were conducted to observe tendency of Tresca stress contour. The model parameters are shown at Table 2. First simulations were conducted by changing t_i and G_{ic} as shown at Table 3 where traction-separation curve was assumed isosceles triangle. The results are shown at Fig. 7. From the results, position of stress concentration along interface depends on the value of G_{ic} and t_i . When t_i was high, Tresca stress more concentrate at one point. In other hand, high G_{ic} created spreading stress concentration. Characteristic lengths of G_{ic} (L_i) and t_i (L_i) were introduced as shown at Fig. 8. In fact, these lengths have relationship with traction separation curve.

After simulating t_i and G_{ic} , several values of interfacial stiffness (K_i) and interfacial friction coefficient (μ_i) were also simulated as shown at Table 4 and 5. The results are shown at Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. For high K_i , stress concentration was shifted far from fiber crack position. In other hand, high μ_i made stress concentration shifted closer to fiber crack position. The results informed that soon after t_i and G_{ic} were determined, K_i and μ_i could be determined by using another characteristic length ($L_{k\&\mu}$).

From simulation results, three characteristic lengths were introduced. The summary of them is shown at Fig. 11. However, theoretically, it is not enough to solve four parameters using three parameters. The final indicator that can be used is Tresca stress contour itself. Using three characteristic lengths reduces complexity in fitting Tresca stress contour from experiment and simulation. It also reduces time consumption to find matching Tresca stress contour.

Table 2. Model parameters for simulations

Parameter	Fiber(T300 ^(a))	Epoxy (EPONResin ^(d))
Elastic modulus (E)	230 GPa ^(b)	3 GPa ^(b)
Poison's ratio (ν_m)	0.2 ^(c)	0.4 ^(c)
Max. elastic strain (ϵ_{max})	1.5% ^(b)	2% ^(b)
Radius model	2.5 mm	25 mm

(a) ToraycaTM fiber, (b) Producer's data sheet, (c) Ref. [5], (d) Polysciences Inc. epoxy, (e) Assumption,

Table 3. Several simulations with different t_i and G_{ic}

Number of Simulation	Interfacial Strength (t_i)	Interfacial Fracture Toughness (G_{ic})
1	10 MPa	0.01
2	20 MPa	
3	10 MPa	0.02
4	20 MPa	

Table 4. Several simulations with different K_i

Number of Simulation	Interfacial Stiffness (K_i)
1	10kN/mm ³
2	50kN/mm ³
3	100kN/mm ³

Table 5. Several simulations with different μ_i

Number of Simulation	Friction Coefficient (μ_i)
1	0
2	0.5
3	1

Fig. 7 The tendency of stress contour due to t_i and G_{ic}

Fig. 8 Characteristic lengths of t and G

Fig. 9 The tendency of stress contour due to K_i

Fig. 10 The tendency of stress contour due to μ_i

Fig. 11 Characteristic length on selected Tresca stress contour

3.2 Single Fiber Fragmentation Test

The scale up from micrometer to millimeter was conducted to demonstrate evaluation of interfacial properties clearly. Carbon pencil with 2B hardness and diameter of 0.5mm was used as fiber. Epoxy resin with polyamidoamine as hardener produced by KONISHI CHEMICAL IND co, Ltd was used as matrix. The specimen was created by using silicon mold with specimen geometry is shown at Fig. 12. Single carbon pencil was placed in the middle of epoxy.

Photo-elasticity technique was used to capture Tresca stress contour in specimen. It can be obtained because epoxy is birefringent material which will have two refraction indexes if there is stress in material. The phenomenon is connected by stress-optic law. A specimen was placed between two polarizers and two retarders. A green monochromatic light source was placed in one side and observed camera in other side. The direction of polarization of two polarizer was perpendicular so that dark image could be obtained when no stress on

specimen. The detail of photo-elasticity technique is shown at Fig. 13.

Before SFFT was conducted, tensile loading was applied to a pure epoxy specimen with displacement rate of 1mm/min. The dark and bright color appeared alternately as shown at Fig. 14. The applied stress was recorded.

The stress-optic coefficient of epoxy (f_σ) was calculated using equation 1.

$$f_\sigma = \sigma_a t / N \quad (1)$$

Where t is thickness of specimen and N is fringe order. The result of f_σ is 10.5 N/mm.

After f_σ was found, tensile loading was applied to a single fiber specimen with same displacement rate. Interfacial debonding appears soon after first carbon pencil fragmentation occurred. It then propagate when strain of 1.4% and applied stress (σ_a) of 3.02MPa. The second fringe order ($N=2$) which indicated observed Tresca stress contour of 4.2MPa was captured as shown at Fig. 15a. The contour was processed by contrasting to find better figure as shown at Fig. 15b.

In fact, observed Tresca stress contour should be corrected due to axis-symmetric effect which cause the Tresca value is not maximum but average value due to light projection as shown at Fig. 16. Schuster proposed corrected stress due to axis-symmetric effect was calculated by equation 2 [6].

$$\sigma_c = \frac{h(\sigma_o - \sigma_a)(r_i - r_o)}{2 \left\{ r_i a - \frac{1}{2} \left(a r_i + (r_o + y)^2 \ln \frac{(a + r_i)}{(r_o + y)} \right) \right\}} + \sigma_n \quad (2)$$

Where, σ_o is observed stress, σ_a is applied stress to specimen, and other parameters are shown at Fig. 16. The parameter a is stated at equation 3.

$$a = [r_i^2 - (y - r_o)^2]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

From equation 2 and 3, the magnitude of corrected Tresca stress is 5.22MPa.

Fig. 12 Normalized ineffective length alteration due to mechanical properties alteration

Fig. 13 Optical arrangement for photo-elasticity

Fig. 16 Axis-symmetric effect on photo-elasticity

Fig. 14 Dark and bright color for (a) $N=0$ and $\sigma_a=0$, (b) $N=0.5$ and $\sigma_a=1.08\text{MPa}$, and (c) $N=1$ and $\sigma_a=2.1\text{MPa}$

Fig. 15 Tresca stress contour of 4.2MPa (a) before contrasting and (b) after contrasting

3.3 Inverse Analysis

In order to conduct inverse analysis, Tresca stress contour at Fig. 15b is picked on top and bottom point and the average is plotted in x-y epoxy plane as shown at Figure 17. The characteristic lengths were then measured and the magnitude of each characteristic length is L_t of 0.428mm, L_G of 0.357mm, and $L_{k\&\mu}$ of 1.964mm. Inverse analysis was conducted by iterating simulations until fit three characteristic lengths and Tresca stress contour of 5.22MPa were obtained. The algorithm of inverse analysis is shown at Fig. 18. It is divided by two sides. One is experimental side to obtain input model parameters and Tresca stress contour and the other is a simulation side.

After several simulations, the match Tresca stress contour was obtained as shown at Fig. 19. The simulated Tresca stress contour was obtained when the values of interfacial properties were shown at Table 6. These values are estimated interfacial properties.

Fig. 17 Plotted Tresca stress contour of 6.2MPa

Fig. 18 Inverse analysis algorithm

Fig. 19 Experiment result (left) and Simulation result (right)

Table 6. Estimated Interfacial Properties	
Interfacial Properties	Value
Interfacial stiffness (K_i)	10^4 N/mm ³
Interfacial strength (t_i)	6 MPa
Interfacial toughness (G_i)	0.022 mJ/mm ²
Friction coefficient (μ_i)	0.1

3.4 Validation of Evaluation Method

Existing interfacial properties evaluations were conducted by using other specimen to compare the evaluation results. Interfacial strength (t_i) was evaluated using shear strength criterion [3]. Tensile loading was applied to a specimen until saturated fragmentation occurs as shown at Figure 20. Interfacial strength was calculated by using equation 4.

$$t_i = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2l_c} \quad (4)$$

Where l_c is critical length which is average of fragmentation length, σ_f is carbon pencil strength (51.7MPa), and d is diameter of carbon pencil. From this method, the magnitude of interfacial strength is 1.72 MPa.

Interfacial fracture toughness (G_{ic}) was evaluated based on energy release criterion [4] which is calculated using equation 5.

$$G_{ic} = \frac{P_c^2}{2\pi d_f} \left(\frac{1}{A_m E_m} - \frac{1}{A_c E_c} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where A_m is matrix cross section, E_m is elastic modulus of matrix, A_c is effective cross section, E_c is effective elastic modulus, and P_c is critical load.

A specimen was loaded until first fiber fragmentation occurs. The specimen was unloaded and loaded again to obtain propagated interfacial debonding on interface. Critical load was determined when interfacial debonding started to propagate. The magnitudes of parameters for calculation were shown at Table 7. The results by using existing method were shown at Table 8. It shows that interfacial strength is lower than estimated value using inverse analysis because in existing method, interfacial debonding is not considered so that it causes underestimate value of interfacial strength. In other hand, evaluation of interfacial fracture toughness using existing method is higher than using inverse analysis. This result occurs because existing method does not consider friction energy which makes overestimate value of interfacial fracture toughness.

Fig. 20 Saturated fragmentation of carbon pencil

Table 7. Parameter for calculating interfacial fracture toughness

Parameter	Value
Epoxy cross section (A_m)	109.8mm ²
Elastic modulus of epoxy (E_m)	216MPa
Effective cross section (A_c)	110mm ²
Effective elastic modulus (E_c)	234.6MPa
Critical load (P_c)	286.4N

Table 8. Parameter for calculating interfacial fracture

Interfacial Properties	Value
Interfacial strength (t_i)	1.2 MPa
Interfacial toughness (G_i)	0.034 mJ/mm ²

4 Conclusion

The technique of interfacial properties evaluation has been developed by utilizing stress contour in matrix. The modeling of single fiber fragmentation test was developed. The characteristic lengths that are related by interfacial properties were found. Inverse analysis was conducted by using characteristic lengths and Tresca stress contour as input parameters. The single fiber fragmentation test using carbon pencil-epoxy specimen was conducted. By using inverse analysis method, The magnitudes of interfacial properties were known i.e. interfacial stiffness of 10000 N/mm², interfacial strength of 6 MPa, interfacial fracture toughness of 0.22mJ/mm², and interfacial friction coefficient of 0.1. Comparison with other method was conducted and it result different value for interfacial strength i.e. 1.2MPa. It is caused by the presence of interfacial debonding which is not considered. By using other method, the interfacial fracture toughness also indicated overestimate result i.e. 0.034mJ/mm³ because the friction work was not considered on the calculation.

The research to compare stress distribution contour as indicator of interfacial properties evaluation is promising because it can evaluate overall interfacial properties. However, image capturing and processing to obtain good picture of stress contour need to be developed in the future and the proposed model still requires further modification.

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